

FAN, TA'LIM, MADANIYAT VA INNOVATSIYA

[Jild: 03 Nashr: 9 (2024)] ISSN: 2992-8915

www.mudarrisziyo.uz

ANALYTICAL INFORMATION ABOUT THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF THE KUSHAN STATE

*Ochildiyev Samandar Shavkatovich*¹

¹ Graduate student of Termiz State University

Abstract: In this article, Kushan period is explained by the fact that there were serious changes in the material and spiritual culture of the peoples of Central Asia. The fate of the Great Kushan kingdom ended tragically from the point of view of spirituality, that is, its history and culture were almost not written during its time. There is very little ancient information about him, and there are not many written monuments either.

Keywords: Kattanahor, Zartepa, Zang Canal, Gaofu, Yuechji, Han, Karatepa, Peshawar, Guyshuan, Tuishuan.

Enter. The emergence of the Kushan state has been the cause of great scientific debate among scientists for a long time. The study of the history of this seemingly legendary kingdom began in the last century. By the 1st century BC, the Tuishuan (Kushon) principality in the five chiefdoms of the Great Yuechi Union became much stronger and expanded its territory. According to the "History of the Last Han Dynasty" (China), "Guishuan ruler Kloqzuko united the remaining four principalities and declared himself the ruler of Buyshuan." The most famous of the kings of the Kushan state is Kanishka. During his rule, the kingdom of Kushans flourished even more. During the period of Kanishka, the provinces of Punjab and Kashmir were annexed to the country. The capital of the country was around Peshawar (Afghanistan). The territory of the country consisted of Northern India, Afghanistan, many regions of Central Asia, and Eastern Turkestan. According to Sima Szyan, "During the reign of Kanishka, his fame spread to the neighboring countries." The country's military power was widely recognized. Those in the western part of China also recognized the rulership of Kanishka and sent him their hostages.

Analysis of literature on the topic. in Central Asia. avv. In IV-II centuries Khorezm, Parthian and Sogdian writings appeared on the basis of Aramaic script. By the Kushan period, another script appeared among them - the Kushan (Bactrian) script. The first monuments were opened in Ayritom and

Kokhna Termiz in the 1930s and continued in the 1960s. Later, the Karatepa Buddhist temple, Fayoztepa, Kholchayon and Dalvarzin ancient towns near the ancient Termiz were opened and the extremely high Kushon culture became famous all over the world. The stone images (waterfall) found on Kesh mountain of the ancient city of Ayritom were known as early as the 30-40s of our century. On these pediments, images of girls dressed in flowers, playing musical instruments, and boys playing drums were depicted. In one of the cotton fields of the city of Denov, Surkhandarya region, the remains of the monument of Holchayan, which was once a large city, have been preserved. The emergence of cities. avv. It corresponds to the middle of the 1st millennium.

The Greco-Bactrian kingdom, which was established in 250 BC, included the Surkhan oasis as well as the large lands of Central Asia. During this reign, socio-economic relations developed in Surkhandarya, and class stratification intensified. Cities flourished. Craftsmanship and foreign trade rose. The cultures of the Greek, Indian and Turanian peoples were combined and a unique high culture was created. The ruins of old buildings of this period were also found in the surroundings of Termiz.

At the beginning of AD, Surkhandarya became part of the Kushan state. The Kushans lived in the place of the Tokharian state for a century, divided into 5 tribes. Kudzula Kadfis, the Yabguzi (ruler) of the Guyshuan (Kushon) tribe, conquered the remaining 4 tribes and declared himself the ruler in the 1st century AD. He made Dalvarzintepa in Surkhandarya the capital. At the beginning of AD, one of the southern branches of the Great Silk Road passed through the first caravan route from China to the countries of the Mediterranean coast through Dalvarzintepa, including the possessions of the Kushan kingdom. This road became very important in the development of foreign trade and culture between countries. The Kushan kingdom became a centralized slave state. The population mainly believed in the Mahayana school of Buddhism. Research methodology. The Buddha statue found in Dalvarzintepa proves this. Kudzula Kadphis, the founder of the Kushan state, quickly conquered India and subjugated northern Bactria. Kadphis II, especially during the reign of Kanishka, the Kushan state expanded and became a powerful kingdom equal to the Roman and Parthian Han (Chinese) kingdoms. The whole of present-day India, Pakistan, Afghanistan, and the southern lands of Central Asia looked at it. The Kushan state ruled from the second half of the 1st century BC to the middle of the 3rd century AD.

There are many and diverse archaeological monuments of the Kushan period in the Surkhandarya region. From the Achaemenid and Greco-Bactrian periods, 40 cities have been known here, and more than 120 cities and villages of the Kushan period have been identified. The population was mainly located along the Sherobod and Surkhandarya basins. Settlement of population, emergence of large and small cities is connected with irrigation canals, of course.

Large and small towns and settlements were located around the central cities in the irrigation basins, which in every way resembled the central city. The central cities, in turn, depended on Termiz, the largest city in Surkhandarya. In this way, residential areas were divided into large cities (Chogoniyon, Termiz), medium cities (Dalvarzintepa, Zartepa), small towns (Jondavlattepa, Talashgantepa, etc.), large and small villages. Of the 120 monuments found, 40 can be included in the list of large cities.

The Kushan kingdom, which ruled in the 1st - 3rd centuries BC, is considered one of the countries that played an important role not only in the history of our country, but also in the economic and cultural development of the peoples of the historical regions of Central Asia. The tribes that founded the Kushan kingdom are called Yuechji and Tokhars in historical sources. In the fourth quarter of the 2nd century BC, the Greco-Bactrian kingdom, which ruled mainly in Bactria, was in crisis due to the march of the Yuechi tribes who lived in the northern regions of Central Asia. By the 1st century AD, Yuechji tribes living in Bactria were divided into five major clans (Khyumi, Shuanmi, Guishuan, Haitun and Gaofu - or Dumis instead of Gaofu in another source) by Kudzula Kadfiz. unified into a single state under

The northern border of the Kushan state is Baysuntag, which is part of the Southern Hisar mountain range, and the Kushan rulers worked tirelessly to strengthen the northern borders of their state.

"Iron Gate" in Boisuntog and its related defense fortifications are one of such structures. During the reign of Vima Kadphiz and especially Kanishka I, the lands of Northern India and Eastern Turkestan were included in this state, and as a result, the Kushan state became a great state standing alongside the Roman Empire, Parthia and Han China of the Old World. At the end of the 3rd century AD, the Kushan state faced a crisis due to internal conflicts and, in particular, the capture of Kushanshahar, i.e. Bactria, by the Sassanid Iranian troops.

The existence of a centralized state for four centuries has led to growth in all aspects of economic and cultural life in Bactria, including the Surkhan oasis, which is part of it.

In the 1st century BC - 1st century AD, the Surkhan oasis was intensively developed, large canals were dug (Kattanahor), existing irrigation facilities were expanded (Zang canal), new cities were founded (Zartepa) or cities such as Termiza (Termiz) and Dalvarzintepa were territorially expanded. The cities of the Kushan period consisted of two parts built on the basis of the project, that is, the archi ala and the main parts of the city adjacent to it. The urbanism of this period is well studied through the religious structures of Dalvarzintepa, Zartepa, Old Termiz and its components, Karatepa, Fayoztepa.

The cities of the Kushan period of the Surkhan oasis served as administrative and economic centers as well as religious centers (Buddhist temples in Karatepa, Fayoztepa, Zartepa, Ayritom and Dalvarzintepa in Old Termiz). At the first stage of the Kushan rule, the intercontinental trade route connecting the countries and peoples of the Old World economically and culturally, the Great Silk Road, was fully formed, and the Kushan state played an important role in this international trade. It occupied

Sculptures created in secular and religious directions, various types of wonderful art, and various handicrafts are distinguished by their non-repetition.

The city of Jizzakh served as a gateway between large cities such as Siberia, Kazakhstan, Shosh, Fergana, Samarkand, Bukhara, Khorasan. In ancient times, the three caravan routes that crossed Mirzachol through Fergana, Oratepa, and Zomin and went straight through Kazakhstan to Nurota joined in Jizzakh and became Ilo. Fayoztepa Temple In 2003-2006, archaeologists from Japan, Russia, France and Germany came to Surkhondarya and continued to excavate Dalvarzintepa, Kholchayon, Budrach, Eski Termiz, Kampirtepa, Fayoztepa, Karatepa and other monuments and made a "diagnosis" of many years of research. . Archaeologists of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek and Termiz State University were at the forefront of these studies. Among them were Jalaliddin Annaev, graduate student of the National University of Uzbekistan, Tokhtash Annaev, a teacher of Termiz State University, candidate of historical sciences, Ismail Botirov, director of the Surkhondarya Archaeological Museum, and other scientists. Thus, a Buddha temple, Bodhisattva statue and other things were also found in Fayoztepa. The most important thing is that this temple occupies a lot of space, so scientists have recognized that this is the best discovery of Buddhism. In the end, they came to the conclusion that Buddhism spread from here to China, India, and Japan. Therefore, in cooperation with the Ministry of Culture and Sports Affairs of Uzbekistan, the representative office of UNESCO in our republic, and Japanese scientific and cultural centers, a small model of this temple was built in Fayoztepa.

Karatepa entered the land of Surkhan - very rich in monuments. Scientific studies report that four to five thousand years ago, agriculture and crafts were extremely developed in the oasis, and the art and culture of the Kushan, Bactrian and Chagarian states were at a good level. It is said that irrigation facilities and even pipes were used at that time, which is evidence of the high intelligence of our ancestors. However, it is known that Buddhism also matured in the 2nd-1st millennium BC. Before the end of the

archaeological excavations in Fayoztepa, everyone was surprised to find another Buddha temple, Buddha statue and other physical evidence in the nearby village, Karatepa. In particular, the Buddhist candle was lit. The artifacts found in the excavations of Dalvarzintepa, Kholchayon, Budrach, Kampirtepa, Jarqo`ton, and Old Termiz proved to be ancient. Eduard Rtvladze, an antiquarian scientist, and Kyuzo Kato, a Japanese historian and archeologist, are of the same opinion. Even Kyuzo Kato, seeing the thorny flower here, had tears in his eyes. He sang the national anthem of Japan, paid tribute to the discovery of the Buddha, and even though he was 84 years old, he was as light as young children. Why do you say? Because, if this temple, statue and other objects are really evidence and it is proved that Buddhism started here, not only Japanese people, even Chinese, Indians and other people belonging to the Buddha religion will come and worship here. Kyuzo Kato went to his country with the intention of announcing the news in Japan, publishing it in the "Oikhonum" magazine, which is published once a year, and organizing an exhibition based on new findings. He always comes back to Surkhandarya and continues the work he started. When Kyuzo Kato was leaving for his homeland, he said: - I am eighty-four years old, I have lived my life. However, because I participated in the Karatepa excavations, even if I die, I will feel happy, he said. By the way, as Fayoztepa and Karatepa entered the language and clarified many things, this is a clear proof that the Uzbek and Japanese peoples have been living in harmony since long ago.

Conclusions and suggestions. Primitive man lived in Central Asia, including Tajikistan, about 200,000 years ago. Late Paleolithic weapons were found in northern and southern Tajikistan. The primitive community system existed in the territory of Tajikistan until the 8th - 7th centuries BC. The transition to the Iron Age began in the 8th and 7th centuries BC. Social and property stratification appeared. In the 6th - 4th centuries BC, the rule of the Iranian state was established on the territory of Tajikistan. At the beginning of the millennium, large irrigation canals were built, urban life, craftsmanship rose to a high level, especially trade with other countries developed rapidly. The Kushon script appeared on the basis of the Greek script. During this period, Buddhism came to Tajikistan from India and Monism from Iran. But Zoroastrianism remained the main religion. In the middle of the 6th century, Tajikistan was incorporated into the Turkic Khanate. Middle Asia was conquered by the Arabs in the middle of the 8th century. As a result of the conquest of Central Asia by the Arabs, Islam became the dominant religion, many cultural monuments and cities were destroyed. The economic and cultural development of the peoples of Central Asia temporarily slowed down. Northern Bactria - A number of Buddhist monuments in Ayritom, Fayoztepa, Karatepa were found in reliable stratigraphic conditions. All this allows us to reconstruct the process of the spread of Buddhism in Central Asia as follows. It seems that some Buddhist preachers started to spread this doctrine in Bactria in II-I centuries BC. However, the mass construction of Buddhist religious structures in northern Bactria, and consequently, the spread of the doctrine in the region, can only be attributed to the second half of the 1st century AD. This is explained by the fact that Bactria and India at that time were part of the single Kushan state.

Archeological materials indicate that Old Termiz was one of the largest centers of Buddhism in the region.

It is located 120 kilometers north-east of Old Termiz (now in Shorchi district). About 36 kg of gold treasure found in Dalvarzintepa, old chess pieces, a house of artisans and potters, various temples, a cemetery of Dalvarzin people - novus, 2 magnificent Buddha structures are proof that this city was once the first capital city of the Kushan kingdom. A Buddhist temple was first discovered in Dalvarzin in 1967. The coins found in the monument were minted during the reign of the Kushan king Kadphiz I (1st century AD). II century Kushan king Vasudeva minted a coin with his image on the helmet. The second temple in Dalvarzin is larger compared to the Buddhist temple outside the city. Excavations began here in 1983. The large Buddha and Badhisatva statues found were made by the Gandhara school of

Buddhist sculpture in northwest India, following the traditions adopted in all areas where Buddhism spread. According to Chinese sources, in the second half of the 2nd century BC, the Yuechi tribes (in fact, the Massagets) living in the regions of Eastern Turkestan were pressured by their neighbors, the Huns, and could not withstand their pressure and moved to the west. The Yuechi met the Sak tribes around Issyk-Kul and pushed them to the southwest. However, the Yuechi were attacked by the Usun tribes, moved to the south and entered the territory of Sogdiya in 130 BC. According to the Chinese historian Zhang Xiang, the Yuechi marched from Sogdia to Bactria and overthrew the rule of the Greeks in Bactria. As stated in Chinese sources, the Yuechi belonged to five main families: Guysh wan (Kushon), Xiumi, Shuanmi, Xise, Dumi. For nearly 100 years, each of them has been a separate political power, a governorship, and has been functioning without being subordinate to a single ruler.

List of references

1. Альбаум Л. И. Балалык-тепе. Ташкент. Издательство Академия наук Уз ССР, 1960.
2. Аннаев Т. Ангор ёдгорликлари. Самарқанд. Ўзбекистон Фанлар Академияси Археология институти нашри. 1991.
3. Боровкова Л. А. Кушанское царство (по древним китайским источникам). М., 2005,
4. Бичурин. Н.Я. (Иакинф). Собрание сведений о народах, обитавших в Средней Азии в древне времена. Т. 2. –М.-Л., 1950.
5. Вертоградова В. В. Индийская эпиграфика Каратепе. М.; Наука, 1996.
6. Yusupovich, Kushakov Safarali. "Material Culture in Zoroastrian Religion." *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education* (2994-9521) 2.6 (2024): 715-719.
7. Юсупович, Қўшоқов Сафарали. "ЗАРДУШТИЙЛИК ДИНИДА ДАФН МАРОСИМЛАР ТАЛҚИНИ." *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH* 3 (2023): 201-208.
8. Yusupovich, Kushakov Safarali. "THE ROLE OF ANCIENT BACTERIA AND MARGIA IN THE ESTABLISHMENT OF ZARDUSTIYA." *Chief Editor* 12.
9. Юсупович, Қўшоқов Сафарали. "ЗАРДУШТИЙЛИК ДИНИ ТАЛҚИНИ ВА УНИНГ МОДДИЙ МАДАНИЯТДА АКС ЭТИШИ." *Scientific Impulse* 1.12 (2023): 246-251.
10. Kushakov, Safarali. "EARLY RELIGIOUS SIGNS OF THE TERRITORIES OF UZBEKISTAN." *Research and Implementation* 1.3 (2023): 71-77.
11. Yusupovich, Kushakov Safarali. "FACTORS WHICH ARE THE BASIS OF THE FIRST RELIGIOUS VIEWS." *Scientific Impulse* 1.11 (2023): 140-145.
12. Юсупович, Қўшоқов Сафарали. "ЗАРДУШТИЙЛИК ДИНИ ТАЛҚИНИ ВА УНИНГ МОДДИЙ МАДАНИЯТДА АКС ЭТИШИ." *Scientific Impulse* 1.12 (2023): 246-251.
13. Yusupovich, Kushakov Safarali. "Orta Osiyoda ilk diniy qarashlarning oziga xosligi." *Scientific Impulse* 1.11 (2023): 115-120.
14. Юсупович, Қўшоқов Сафарали. "ЗАРДУШТИЙЛИК ДИНИ ТАЛҚИНИ ВА УНИНГ МОДДИЙ МАДАНИЯТДА АКС ЭТИШИ." *Scientific Impulse* 1.12 (2023): 246-251.